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Impact of Visual Merchandising on Young Customers' Apparel Impulse Buying Behavior

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Abstract-This study attempts to explore the effect of visual merchandising on young customers' impulse buying behavior. The purpose of this paper is to study the influence of selected visual merchandising techniques on young customers' impulse buying behavior. To attain this objective a study was carried out among shoppers in the age group of 16-35 years. In this study, hypotheses were formulated to investigate relationships between the customers' tendency to purchase on impulse (dependent variable) and four techniques of visual merchandising (independent variables): window display, mannequin/in-store form display, floor merchandising and promotional signage. Survey was administered using a structured questionnaire among 677 shoppers who constituted the sample. These were shoppers who were visiting retail outlets at various shopping malls in different parts of Bangalore, India. With the help of SPSS, reliability test, factor analysis, correlation and linear regression have been run on the data to get the findings. The results of the present study prove that there is a pivotal relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and various visual merchandising practices. The findings are useful for retailers to perceive the nature of impulse.

Keywords: Customer behavior; Impulse buying; Visual merchandising

1. Introduction:

With globalization and the retail boom, visual merchandising is growing in leaps and bounds. It is not simply concerned about decorating a store beautifully but must also symbolize the brand keeping the target audience in mind. The similarity of merchandise is forcing the retailers to focus on visual merchandising to improve the desirability of product, differentiate their offering and to enhance impulse buying. Visual Merchandising is the art of displaying merchandise in a manner that is appealing to the eyes of the customer. Apparel retailers, especially, place more importance on visual merchandising to differentiate their offerings from others'. Researchers found that impulse buyers usually do not set out with the specific purpose of visiting a certain store and purchasing a certain item; the behavior occurs after experiencing an urge to buy [1], and such behaviors are influenced by internal states and environmental/external factors. Since impulse buying is a pervasive aspect of consumers' behaviors and a focal point for strategic marketing plans

[2], it is worthwhile for retailers to understand factors within the retail setting that trigger consumers' impulsive reactions. One of the factors could be attributed to the concept of visual merchandising. Visual merchandising is the art of presentation, which puts the merchandise in focus and in perspective too. It educates the customers, creates desire and finally augments the selling process. It is often underestimated and overlooked by many retailers, yet it is a vital part of the retail business and adds enormous value. It is a nascent area of Indian retail industry therefore a study on visual merchandising will go a long way in addressing this gap. This study attempts to identify and explain the impact of visual merchandising on impulse buying among young customers.

2. Literature Review:

2.1. *Impulse Buying:*

Research scholars have taken a very keen interest in impulse buying for the past sixty years ([2],[3],[4]). Reference [4] provided the foundation for defining impulse buying behavior by classifying the act as planned, unplanned, or impulse. Planned buying behavior involves a time-consuming information search followed by rational decision making, while unplanned buying behavior relates to all purchases made without such advance planning and includes impulse buying, which is distinguished by the relative speed with which buying "decisions" occur. In addition to being unplanned, an impulse purchase involves experiencing a sudden, strong, and irresistible urge to buy. Reference [5] defines the buying impulsiveness trait as "a consumer's tendency to buy spontaneously, unreflectively, immediately and kinetically". The marketing literature describes impulse buying as an unplanned purchase made as a consequence of sudden, powerful and persistent urge to buy products immediately ([1], [2]). Reference [6] reported that impulse buying has been lately conceptualized as a sudden, compelling, hedonically complex purchasing behavior in which the rapidity of the purchase decision process excludes thoughtful, deliberate consideration of all information and choice. Impulse buying occurs after shoppers experience spontaneous urges to buy with little or no reflection about the purchase decision and it is characterized by rapid decision making, subjective bias in favor of immediate possession and diminished regards for its consequences ([2],[5]). The unplanned nature of the purchase is central to the definition of impulse buying [7]. Impulse buying is also described as a form of hedonic rather than utilitarian shopping behavior underpinned by several pervasive emotional motivations [8]. Impulse buying is considered as relevant in today's shopping scenario with the innovative sales promotions, creative messages and appropriate use of technologies in the retail stores. The powerful influence of impulse behavior

on consumer buying suggests it is an important area of study [9]. Reference [10] found that the examination of impulse buying in super markets could be of much interest to the manufacturers as well as retailers worldwide. We expect higher impulse buying tendency to increase the likelihood of purchase incidence at retail trade shows ([1],[10]).

2.1.1. Factors Influencing Impulse Buying:

a. External Stimuli and Store Environment:

External factors of impulse buying refer to marketing cues or stimuli that are placed and controlled by the marketer in an attempt to lure consumers into purchase behavior [11]. External Stimuli are related to the shopping and the marketing environment. The shopping environments include the store size, ambience, design and formats while the marketing environment is the various sales and advertising activities. Buying impulses can be induced when a consumer encounters a relevant visual stimulus in the retail environment, or some promotional stimuli [7]. Reference [12] was the first to suggest that impulse purchasing may stem from the consumer's exposure to a stimulus while in the store. The various stimuli inside the shop directly or indirectly influence the customer. Reference [13] stated that store environments influence the consumers' emotional states which may further lead to impulse buying inside the store. Reference [14] emphasized that buying impulses actually begin with a consumer's sensation and perception driven by the external stimulus, and are followed by a sudden urge to buy (I see I want to buy). Reference [15] found that store environmental stimuli positively affect impulse buying behavior especially when the store environment is perceived as over-stimulating (excitement and stimulation). Stimuli in the retail store environment are likely to affect consumer emotions [16], which are other variables that have been found to affect the impulse purchases ([2],[17]). Reference [17] described that informative and experiential aspect of POP poster may influence impulse buying. Reference [18] carried out an experimental study to study the influence of music along with that of scent. Findings demonstrated significance of both the attributes in isolation as well as in combination with each other. Reference [17] classified the in-store shopping environment into two distant effects i.e. the promotional, informative and economic effect, and the atmospheric engagement effect. The promotional effect consists of stimuli like promotional discounts (coupons, multiple-item discounts and gifts) and cheaper prices, while atmospheric engagement effect include stimuli of enjoyment and attractiveness like in-store advertisements, store displays, salesperson, shop crowding etc. Also it has been suggested that marketing innovations such as credit cards, cash machines, instant credit, 24-hour retailing, and telemarketing make it easier than ever before for consumers to buy things on

impulse ([2], [5]). Manufacturers and retailers spend huge amount of money on marketing their brands to consumers, with the aim of increasing awareness, trial usage, and ultimately market share. Hence, manufacturers and retailers need information on the effectiveness of in-store stimuli and the extent to which they influence consumer purchasing behavior. This information can help them determine the efficiency of resources designed to stimulate additional sales as well as differentiate themselves from competitors.

b. Internal Stimuli:

Internal Stimuli are related to the different personality related factors which characterizes an individual rather than the shopping environment or stimuli. Internal factors of impulse buying denote the individual's internal cues and characteristics that make him / her engage in impulse buying. One of the path breaking researches by reference [14] highlighted that it is people and not the product, which experience the consuming impulses during a shopping spree. Reference [2] suggested that consumer impulsivity is a lifestyle trait which can be linked to materialism, sensation seeking, and recreational aspects of shopping. Reference [5] introduced the concept of buying impulsiveness trait which shows a person's tendency to involve in impulsive shopping. Reference [11] pointed out that impulse buying may originate from consumer traits such as impulsiveness and optimum stimulation level, shopping enjoyment, or lack of self-control. Reference [8] categorized impulse buying as hedonic behavior that is associated with feelings and psychosocial motivations instead of thinking and functional benefits. Reference [1] suggested that impulse purchasing is associated with sensory stimulation and hedonic motivation. Fashion involvement and positive emotion had positive effects on consumers' fashion-oriented impulse buying behavior with fashion involvement having the greatest effect. Hedonic consumption tendency was an important mediator in determining fashion-oriented impulse buying [19].

c. Situational and Product Related factors:

Situational factors influencing impulse buying may include actual or perceived time available and spending power [1]. Relationship between the store environment and the consumer's impulsive moods is moderated by the situational factors such as time pressure [13]. In-store browsing appears to be positively affected by one's available time and one's impulse buying tendency, and in turn, has a positive impact on one's positive feelings and impulse buying urge [1]. Reference [4] initially observed that the different aspects of the product which is encountered in the store may affect impulse buying. Factors such as consumers' financial position, time pressure, social visibility and emotional states mediate the transition from felt urge to buy to actual impulse purchases ([1],

[5]).Reference [4]identified nine product-related factors that might be influential: low price; marginal need for the product/brand; mass distribution; self-service; mass advertising; prominent store display; short product life; small size; ease of storage. This suggests products that are more expensive and require more time and effort (high involvement purchases) are less likely to be bought on impulse.

d. Demographics and Socio-Cultural factors:

Reference [20] found that the characteristics of consumers and their demographics influence the impulse purchasing. Reference [21] observed that gender, as a social category, affects impulse buying. Men tend to involve in impulse buying of instrumental and leisure items which projects their independence and activity. Women tend to buy the symbolic and self-expressive goods which are associated with their appearance and emotional aspects of self. Dramatic increases in personal disposable incomes and credit availability have made impulse buying in retail environments prevalent consumer behavior [21]. Reference [15] highlighted that social factors influence impulse buying. Social factors include two types: store employees and other customers. Social factor (e.g. employee friendliness) was found to directly influence impulse buying. Store managers might be able to reduce the negative effect of crowding by training their employees to be extra friendly at busy times. Reference [22] argued that in a cultural context, the theory of individualism and collectivism gives important insights about consumer's impulsive behavior.

2.2. Visual Merchandising:

Both practitioners and academicians particularly have long considered visual stimulation and communication as important aspects of retail store environment [23].Visual merchandising is not a mere arrangement of products but goes deeper and wider into the essence of physicality of the store [24]. It can be viewed as all the things the shopper witnesses, both exterior and interior, which shape a constructive impression of the store and result in higher purchase action at the shoppers' end. Visual merchandising is therefore concerned with both how the product and/or brand is visually communicated to the customer and also whether this message is decoded appropriately in the context affecting a positive psychological or behavioral outcome, ultimately leading to purchase [23]. Out of the major variables that were studied as factors of visual merchandising, window displays and in-store promotional signage have a great positive impact on consumer's impulse buying behavior [25].Reference [23]suggested that the use of a wide variety of colors is deemed to produce attractive and appealing display and had the potential to positively impact on a respondent's propensity to browse. More recently, reference [26] also asserted that visual merchandising enhances store image

and consumer shopping experience at the store, adding value to the store character. They found, in particular, that spatial orientation within the store and well-designed visual merchandising display affects consumers' perception on the retail store. Furthermore, results of their study indicated that consumers perceive visual merchandising as a promotional tool. Signage is also an important aspect of visual merchandising; customers should be able to purchase the product without any help of salesperson ([14], [27]). Window display is an important criterion of visual merchandising as it creates first impression of the store on the customers ([27], [28]). Reference [29] also asserted that visual merchandising covers the store exterior and interior that is involved in creating a favorable shopping atmosphere which can enhance consumers' perceived image of the store. Visual Merchandising is the presentation of merchandise as well as a store in order to attract customers. It is an attractive way and an eye-catching technique to tell customers what the store stands for and offers to its potential customers [30]. Mannequins used in visual merchandising provide information that adds to consumers' cognitive understanding of products and their social acceptability [31].

3. Research Hypotheses:

In this study, customers' impulse purchase tendency serving as a shopper characteristic and visual merchandising serving as an external cue are determined to be variables. Therefore, the following hypotheses were developed to investigate relationships between customers' tendency to purchase on impulse and four types of visual merchandising: window display, in-store form/mannequin display, floor merchandising and promotional signage.

H₁. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by widow display.

H₂. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by in sore form/mannequin display.

H₃. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by floor merchandising.

H₄. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by promotion signage.

4. Research Methodology:

4.1. Instrument Design:

The questionnaire consisted of six major sections measuring demographics, customers' impulse buying tendency, and influence of visual merchandising. The first section of the questionnaire consisted of questions to determine the respondents' demographic profile, such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, educational qualification and income. The second section of the questionnaire measured customers' impulse buying tendency. Sections three through the section six included questions measuring four distinctive visual merchandising practices that were expected to

influence customers' impulse buying tendency. These were window display, in-store form/mannequin display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage. A five point LIKERT scale, ranging from never=1 to always=5 was used to measure each variable. Respondents were asked to circle the number that best described their response.

4.2. Research and Sample Design:

The study was intended to focus on the impact of visual merchandising in terms of apparel segment as a product category. The research design used is descriptive. The sample size of the research was 700 but 23 were outliers hence, the revised sample size was 677. The sampling technique was mall intercept method. Customers who walk out of the store were surveyed with the help of structured questionnaire. Thus, sampling procedure is purposive sampling. The survey was conducted in various Malls of Bangalore for fifteen days.

4.3. Data Analysis Methods:

Prior to questionnaire administration, a statistician was consulted to ensure the questions would be applicable for analysis and also to determine the suitable statistical tools to be used for this research. Data collected were entered into an Excel file. The data file was imported from Excel to the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences' (SPSS) software for analysis. Statistical methods used for the data analysis in this study were descriptive statistics and frequency tests, principal component analysis and reliability tests, Pearson correlation tests, and regression analysis. The significance level chosen for this study was .01.

The outline for analysis is as follows: First, descriptive statistics and frequency tables are generated. Then, Principal Component Analysis for data reduction and reliability test are conducted. The Pearson Correlation test is conducted to check the correlations between impulse buying tendency and each of the four types of visual merchandising practices. Finally, Linear Regression Analysis is conducted for hypothesis testing to find out the relationships between impulse buying tendency and each of the four types of visual merchandising practices. The descriptive statistics for each variable is shown in Table I. In the questionnaire different items including three to five items were developed to measure each variable under study. We apply Principal component analysis with Varimax rotation to reduce these measures into single variable. Furthermore internal consistency was checked using Cronbach's alpha to ensure the reliability of data reduction. Table II reveals that all of items have a factor loading of 0.5 or greater which shows each item belongs to only one group.

5. Hypothesis Testing:

H₁. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by window displays.

In the result of a Pearson correlation test, a significant correlation was shown between impulse buying and window display with a p-value less than .001 (Table III). Since the p-value ($p < .001$) ($r=0.404$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, the data provided sufficient evidence that window display was significantly related with customers' impulse buying behavior. In consistence with the result of the correlation test, the regression analysis found that window display significantly influenced customers' impulse buying behavior (Table IV). The p-value ($p < .001$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, supporting the researcher's hypothesis. The data provided sufficient evidence that there was a significant relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and window display. This result suggests that window display significantly influences customers' impulse buying behavior.

H₂. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by in-store form/mannequin display.

A Pearson correlation test resulted in a small p-value ($p < .001$) ($r=0.422$) for the second hypothesis, suggesting a significant correlation between impulse buying and in-store form/mannequin display (Table III). The data provided sufficient evidence that in-store form/mannequin display was significantly related to customers' impulse buying behavior. In consistence with the result of the correlation test, the regression analysis found that in-store form/mannequin display significantly influenced customers' impulse buying behavior (Table IV). The p-value ($p < .001$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, supporting the researcher's hypothesis. The data provided sufficient evidence that there was a significant relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and in-store form/mannequin display. This result suggests that in-store form/mannequin display significantly influences customers' impulse buying behavior.

H₃. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by floor merchandising.

The result of a Pearson correlation test found a significant correlation between impulse buying and floor merchandising (Table III). The p-value ($p < .001$) ($r=0.305$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, suggesting that the data provided sufficient evidence that floor merchandising was significantly related with customers' impulse buying behavior. In addition, the regression analysis found that floor merchandising significantly influenced customers' impulse buying behavior (Table IV). The p-value ($p < .001$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, suggesting that the data provided sufficient evidence that there was a significant directional relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and floor merchandising.

**TABLE I
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OR VARIABLES**

Variables	No. of Cases	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	676	2.9063	0.66859
Influence of Window Display	677	2.9151	0.93797
Influence of Mannequin Display	677	3.0032	0.82775
Influence of Floor Merchandising	677	3.0153	0.94207
Influence of Promotional Signage	677	3.1558	0.91356

H₄. Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by promotional signage.

A Pearson correlation test found a significant correlation between impulse buying and promotional signage with a p-value less than .001 (Table III). Because the p-value ($p < .001$) was smaller than an alpha level of .01, the result suggested that the data provided sufficient evidence that promotional signage was significantly related with customers' impulse buying behavior. As expected, the regression analysis found that promotional signage significantly influenced customers' impulse buying behavior (Table IV). The p-value ($p < .001$) was smaller than an alpha level .01, suggesting that the data provided sufficient evidence that there was a significant directional relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and promotional signage. This result was expected because the result of the Pearson correlation test showed much higher coefficient ($r = .444$) for the relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and influence of promotional signage. This result suggests that promotional signage significantly influenced customers' impulse buying behavior.

**TABLE II
FACTOR ANALYSIS RESULTS**

Factor	Item	Factor Loading	Eigen value	% of Variance	Alpha Coefficient
Impulse Buying Tendency	I go shopping to change my mood	0.584	2.027	40.545	0.633
	I buy things spontaneously	0.614			
	I feel a sense of excitement when I make an impulse purchase	0.629			
	I have difficulty controlling my urge to buy when I see a good offer	0.689			
	When I see a good deal, I tend to buy more than that I intended to buy	0.663			
Influence of Window Display	I tend to enter a store when I am attracted by an eye-catching window display	0.764	2.171	54.273	0.711
	I feel compelled to enter the store when I see an interesting window display	0.809			
	I tend to choose the store to shop in depending on eye-catching window display	0.772			
	I tend to buy the clothing which is on window displays	0.580			

Influence of Mannequin Display	I get an idea of what I want to buy after looking through in-store /mannequin display	0.689	1.947	48.674	0.641
	When I see clothing featuring a new style or design on display, I tend to buy it	0.751			
	When I see clothing that I like on in-store form/mannequin display, I tend to buy it	0.768			
	I tend to rely on store displays when I make a decision to purchase clothing	0.565			
Influence of Floor Merchandising	When I see clothing that catches my eye I tend to try it on without looking through the whole section	0.785	1.682	56.066	0.607
	When I walk along the aisle, I tend to look through the clothing close to me	0.689			
	I tend to try on clothing that catches my eye when I pass by	0.769			
Influence of Promotional Signage	If I see an interesting promotional offer on in-store signs, I tend to buy	0.708	2.193	54.824	0.721
	Sale/clearance signs entice me to look through the clothing	0.788			
	When I see a special promotion sign, I go to look at that clothing	0.759			
	I am more likely to make an unintended purchase if the clothing has a sale or clearance sign	0.703			

**TABLE III
CORRELATION WITH IMPULSE BUYING**

Variables	Coefficient(r)	Significance (p)
Window Display	0.404	0.000
Mannequin Display	0.422	0.000
Floor Merchandising	0.305	0.000
Promotional Signage	0.444	0.000

**TABLE IV
FINAL RESULT OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS**

Hypothesis	B	p-value	β	t-statistics
H ₁ .Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by window display	0.288	0.000	0.404	11.460
H ₂ .Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by in-store form/mannequin display	0.341	0.000	0.422	12.082
H ₃ .Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by floor merchandising	0.216	0.000	0.305	8.304
H ₄ .Customers who purchase on impulse are influenced by promotional signage.	0.325	0.000	0.444	12.851

6. Findings and Conclusion:

The concept of how merchandising influences store traffics has received little attention in past studies. With the purpose of answering the question of why customers buy on impulse, this study was carried out to investigate some of the external factors that influence customers' impulse buying behavior. To examine this relationship further, this study attempted to explain the relationship between customers' impulse buying behavior and various types of visual merchandising. The key discovery of this learning was that visual merchandising practices certainly influence customers' impulse buying behavior. The results proved that there were significant relationships between

customers' impulse buying behavior and window display, in-store/mannequin display, floor merchandising and promotional signage.

The findings of this study provided sufficient evidence that retailers can effectively utilize visual merchandising to increase desirability of products, to help customers become aware of the products, and to create favorable attitudes. As organized retailing is gaining momentum there is no doubt that Visual Merchandising will play a significant role in apparel retailing in the future.

7. Managerial Implications:

Retailers must use these findings efficaciously to increase sales of their stores and innovate themselves in terms of display. Window display is a dimension which helps retailers to fetch customers inside the store. It is the first impression of the store. Hence, all retail outlets must have a strong window display. Product display should be well organized so that customers do not have to work hard in search of the product they want to purchase. Mannequin should display best of the merchandise so that customer sees it and can think how the same would look on them and can empathize with the apparel. Promotional signage and floor display will enhance the experience of the store. Retailers should focus on these dimensions in order to increase sales of the store.

8. Limitations of Study:

This research suffered from the following limitations:

- The data was collected from Bangalore and the sample was geographically limited. The data from other cities may produce different results.
- The mechanism was limited to a quantitative method. The survey asked participants to answer the questions based on their recent impulse buying experiences as long as they were aware of their behavior and influences. However, the qualitative research for this may differ in outcome.

9. Scope for future study:

The present study focuses on the respondents in Bangalore city only. The same study could be conducted in different cities to understand the similarity of customers' impulse buying behavior towards apparel purchase decision. Further the study can be focused on rural and urban population, and customers of all age groups to find out if there is any difference in opinion among them.

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